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Plurality of Justice in Indian Detective Fiction: A Postmodern Study

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Abstract:

The genre of modern detective fiction travelled to India from the West in a form ready for the consumption of the reading population. Although the lineage of detective fiction in India can be traced back to the Vedic age, this modern form of detective fiction has been a genre produced in India as late as the late nineteenth century. Traveling from west to east in a form ready for consumption by readers, this genre implemented colonial superiority over the colonized masses. However, the Indian detective fiction written during the post-modern age challenged this colonial enterprise of monopolization of justice and truth. This paper aims to deal with three short Indian detective fictions of the post-modern era, namely “The Rhythm of the Riddles” by Saradindu Bandyopadhyay, “Lethal Air by Suchitra Bhattacharya, and “A Death Considered” by Anil Menon. The post-structuralist change in the interpretation of justice in the detective fiction of the subcontinent is evident. The raging debate of “modernism” and “post-modernism” initiated by the publication of Lyotard’s “Postmodern Condition” has been inseparable from the question of the political, practical, and social experience. The post-colonial Indian detective fiction, moving away from the colonial fixed notions of justice and singular truth, portrays truth and justice through the changing perspectives. This paper aims to study this change in the notion of justice and truth through the lens of the post-modern incredulity towards metanarratives.

Keywords: Postmodern; Metanarrative; Justice; Colonial; Indian Detective fiction.

Introduction

Any literature produced in India before the colonial influence cannot be considered a part of the genre of modern detective fiction. Scholars like M K Naik and Sukumar Sen in their various works have tried to explain and place various elements of this category of fiction in the massive body of Indian literature. Indian literature has the heritage of various mystery fictions, fictions related to murders and supernatural elements in various forms. Pulp literature, being the literature of the masses, has been primarily written in various vernaculars in India. The modern detective fiction, for instance, first began to be written in Bangla followed by Tamil and Hindi. Interestingly, the number of detective fiction written in English during the nineteenth and first half of the twentieth century is meagre. Some of the prominent works among them were “The Prince of Destiny: The New Krishna” (1909) by Sarath Kumar, which was more of a socio-political novel with some detective elements, “The Verdict of the Gods” (1905) by Bal Gangadhar Tilak, and “The Missing Memsahib” (1911) by H. K. Roy. The significant phase of Indian detective fiction in English begins with the translation of vernacular detective fiction into English for a pan Indian readership. Later, with the increase of English readers in India, popular literature came to be written in English. These English authors are from different parts of India. The locale of their plot is usually set in different terrain and locality of India.

Now, these detective fictions are produced for a group of readers who belong to post-Independence India. This readership has witnessed the massacre of Partition, many riots, corruption, along colonial brutality. On the other hand, the writers of these detective fictions are also part of the same population. Thus, a sense of disbelief in the idea of the European Enlightenment challenging age-old legal systems is very prominent in their minds. Alongside, the post-World War II world became extremely disillusioned and started to break away from

principles of metanarratives like the European Enlightenment, developing civilizations, scientific beliefs of the eventual development of humanity over time, and others. These led to post-structuralist analysis of various vectors of society. Literature, being one of the most vital attributes of societal culture, was scrutinized through post-structuralist lenses. Decentralization of literary genres and forms impacted literature in numerous ways. Authors started experimenting with form, idea, themes, and whatnot. Similar was the case with Indian detective fiction. The so-called definition of justice, which is delivered by the legal system, started to be contested.

In the instance of Indian detective fiction, the genre's core formula was frequently changed. European creation of a calculative device in place of a detective came to be questioned. All these shifts framed this contemporary Indian detective fiction in many ways.

Literature Review

The study in the field of detective fiction of the west and east, particularly India, have been carried through a set of texts dealing with the history, structure and social impact of the genre, while the study to understand the postmodern conditions have been made through a set of literary works and books written for understanding and interpreting postmodernist incredulity towards metanarratives.

"Detective Fiction," the first bibliographical study, was written by John Carter and published in *New Paths in Book Collecting* in 1934. Robert P. Ashley wrote an article titled "Wilkie Collins and the Detective Story" (1951), dealing with the significance of the first English detective novel. Hutter, in his "Dreams, Transformations, and Literature: The Implications of Detective Fiction" (1975), discusses the idea of imagination, mystery, and transformation in Detective fiction. Winks emphasized the impact of detective fiction among early twentieth-century readers in his article "American Detective Fiction" in the *Journal of American Studies*

in 1980. A structural study of Italian detective fiction was done by JoAnn Cannon in his “The Detective Fiction of Leonardo Sciascia” (1983). Taye Assefa, in her “Detective Fiction in Amharic” (1999), studied the detective genre in the literatures of the nations with a colonial past, particularly North Africa. In “From Detective Stories to Detective Novels” (1983), Leitch studies the movement from detective stories to detective novels. Research in understanding the structure of detective fiction led to theoretical works like Dorothy Slater’s “Aristotle on Detective Fiction” (2013). This work particularly relates Aristotle’s diction on tragedy with plot, structure, characters, events, and emotions in detective fiction. Clues turned out to be epistemological models in the late nineteenth century. The paradigm of clues and myth has been traced right from Morelli’s detection of the original masterpiece to the detection technique of Doyle’s Sherlock Holmes by Carlo Ginsburg in his essay “Myth, Clues and the Evidential Paradigm” (2013). This essay discusses the approach of Holmes' detection through observation of the trivial details. The social aspects of this genre of literature, the interpretation of justice and laws in the detective fiction, are looked at by Kate Morrison in “Morality and Law in British Detective and Spy Fiction, 1880-1920” (2020).

Although the genre became popular in India around the same time as in Britain, Indian detective fiction has emerged as a recent field of study in the last few decades of the twentieth century. Priya Joshi, in her book “In Another Country: Colonialism, Culture, and the English Novel in India” (2002), states that, nearly around the same time that detective books first appeared in Britain, particularly those by Collins and Doyle, they were also available in Indian public libraries.

Sukumar Sen’s “*Crime Kahinir Kala Kranti*” (1988) studies the beginnings of detective fiction from the Vedic ages to the postmodern Indian scenes. The history of Hindi detective fiction is covered in detail in Francesca Orsini's 2009 book "Print and Pleasure, Popular Literature and Entertaining Fictions in Colonial North India," which examines the late nineteenth-century

modern Hindi detective fictions as translations of Bangla detective fictions and the subsequent changes that led to the emergence of new forms of the genre over time.

A recent journal article by scholars of Raiganj University, named “The History of Detective Fiction in India and Abroad,” reads the course of Indian detective fiction through the lenses of postcolonial criticism. It highlights Bandyopadhyay’s Byomkesh to be an Indianized detective character. His characteristics are unlike the previous detectives of Indian fiction, who were mere colonial versions of their imperial counterparts.

Indian detective fiction written mostly during the colonial period was overpowered by the colonial legal system and justice. The postmodern detective fiction, beginning from the works of Saradindu Bandyopadhyay, challenges the colonial institution of justice and the metanarrative of civilizing the natives through various plots.

Lyotard’s “Postmodern Condition: A Report on Knowledge” (1984) for the first time raises the question of the commodification of knowledge and the idea of post-modern incredulity towards metanarrative. His “Just Gaming” (1985) focuses on the all-encompassing colonial ideals of justice. Terry Eagleton's 1983 work "Literary Theory: An Introduction" emphasizes how capitalism has influenced humanities perspectives.

Works like “Can the Subaltern Speak” (1988) by Spivak, or “Orientalism” (1978) by Said have emphasized the colonial oppression of the colonized. Indian detective fiction has been studied through various lenses, but the context of the idea of plurality of justice has not yet been highlighted.

Discussion

Saradindu Bandyopadhyay’s “The Rhythm of the Riddles” was written somewhere around the 1950s. The backdrop of its plot is the event of India’s independence from British imperial rule. The story is set in ‘a three-storeyed building’ in which Byomkesh, along with his wife Satyavati

and his friend Ajit, stayed. This family occupied five rooms on the third storey of the mentioned building. The concept of a detective living with his family was radical. The stories that worked as models for Indian detective fiction writers portrayed detectives with no familial ties or emotions. The stories of Holmes presented Indian characters as outsiders in London, which can be evident from Doyle's novel "The Sign of the Four". Although elements of Victorian identity had already shaped the culture and identity of the people residing in Bengal, and Bengali "*Bhodrolok*" was one such conditioning of Bengali men. Bhupesh Babu, a significant character in the detective plot of the story, is introduced as a "*Bhodrolok*". His Indian attire and appearance reflect his culture and affluence of social status. Bhupesh Babu is also said to be "slightly western in tastes". This highlights the state of otherness of the West in the works of Bandyopadhyay.

The reason behind the murder becomes very significant. It raises the greater question of justice and the consequential question of punishment. This challenges the role and function of the detective. This also questions the metanarrative of the European Enlightenment and the civilizing of the natives. India gained independence from the Imperial British rule on 15th August 1947, but this was achieved at the cost of the Partition of the country on the basis of religion. This Partition resulted in a massacre, causing millions of deaths and loss of properties. The Partition of the country was an impact of the imperial rule on the entire sub-continent. This violence is highlighted through the crime in the story. The detective Byomkesh identifies the murderer, but does not inform the police about the same. To the readers, the ending appears just. While the arch of the narrative of justice, which is defined by legal laws, would have pointed otherwise. The murder victim, Natabar Babu, was responsible for the death of the son and wife of Bhupesh Babu. Bhupesh Babu was tricked, looted, and his son was abducted and killed by Natabar Babu. This was during the riots in Dhaka, which were the consequence of the Partition of India. Bhupesh Babu, losing his everything, was forced to cross borders and

settle down in Calcutta. Natabar Babu could not be legally convicted due to the loss of evidence and the turmoil that the nation went through during the partition and post-partition years. Nevertheless, being a murderer, he deserved a similar fate himself. Hence, even though the legal system could not guarantee justice to those like Bhupesh Babu, this post-modern Indian detective fiction provided justice to him. The colonial set of legal laws and education, though, have proclaimed to have civilized the otherwise barbarian society of India, but it turns incapable of providing justice to a Partition victim like Bhupesh Babu. Thus, Saradindu's story proves incredible to the colonial metanarrative of justice and civilizing the natives.

In another story, "Lethal Air" by Suchitra Bhattacharya, translated into English by Radha Chakravarty, the legal idea of justice is again questioned. Soumyarup Chaudhuri was found dead at his home. It was a multi-storeyed apartment, named Akashleena, in Alipore. No marks of violence were found on his body. His wife was suspected and taken into police custody. Mitin, the private detective, looked into the case on her own. It was finally found that the mother of the victim had administered a drug into her disabled son's intravenous channel and caused his death. This act of euthanasia, which means the "good death", was performed by the mother of Soumyarup. This was based on the mission of eradicating the pain of her son. Mitin was bent on saving the innocent wife of the victim. But she could also realise the killing carried out by the mother was out of mercy for her son, intending to free him from the physical and mental agony. The detective Mitin succeeded in identifying the murderer and understanding the motive behind the crime. But the story ends with her stuck in an ideological and emotional struggle in order to save her wife as well as her mother. She believes that an old, widowed mother bent on killing her son is already going through a lot of torture from within. While terminating the life of her son has also, in all senses, been a mercy on him. Here, the detective can solve her case. Yet does not succeed in her motive of saving the innocent before the story

ends. The reader is left with an open-ended plot to interpret on their own. Thus, the idea of legal justice is challenged again.

Anil Menon's "A Death Considered" is a deconstructive plot. Unlike the genre fiction, no crime takes up, but the reader is kept engaged throughout the story, expecting the crime to happen. The plot points finger at the readers. It claims that the crimes of detective fiction thrive on them. The very concept of the structure of detective stories is challenged through this story. The structure of detective fiction, as discussed by Sukumar Sen, is centered on the crime and is divided primarily into three parts. The first part of the story introduces the circumstances in which the crime is to take place and the happening of the crime, and the second part discusses the solving of the crime, and the final part is the conclusion. This story by Menon begins with an introduction of the characters and the circumstances of the crime to take place. It further discusses six possible murders and their reasons and consequences. Finally, the story ends with the reader speculating about their intentions. This post-modern detective fiction breaks away from the notions of justice and the typical plot structure of detective stories, highlighting the role of storytelling and narratives over the conventional structure of such fiction.

Conclusion

The paper studies three detective short stories written in postmodern India in the light of incredulity towards metanarrative and the multiplicity of justice. It studies the implementation of the function of emotions and sensibility in the Indian genre of detective fiction and finds the detectives to be valuing the emotional ties in their own lives. The idea of justice beyond laws regulated by colonial ideologies is explored and found to be decentralised, which justifies the plurality of justice. The changes in the structure of detective fiction are studied further through the lens of deconstruction theory.

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